

Factors Affecting English as a Foreign Language Learners' Participation on Speaking in Classroom of Preparatory Schools in Kembata Tembaro Zone.

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Abstract: The main objective of this study was to investigate the factors affecting EFL (English as a Foreign Language) learners' participation in speaking lesson in English classrooms on some selected preparatory schools in Kembata Tembaro Zone. It was a descriptive study. The study employed both qualitative and quantitative research methods to investigate the problem in the schools. Twelve (12) English teachers and three hundred (300) students from Shinshicho, Hedero and Doyogena were taken as a sample population. Therefore, from 300 students, 147=males and 153=females were taken as sample representatives of participants of the study. Students were selected using through simple random sampling techniques. From total twelve teachers at Shinshicho, Hedero and Doyogena Preparatory Schools. They selected using through availability sampling techniques. The instruments that were used for data collection were: questionnaire, interview, and classroom observations. Six selected teachers from some selected preparatory school and eight students who filled the questionnaire were selected by using purposive sampling techniques and they were interviewed. The findings were described through using frequencies/percentage and narrative description. Analysis of the data was ran descriptively. The results of the study indicated that the students faced many problems in relation to teacher, teaching resources and students' their own role related factors, like: teachers way of teaching, class sizes, lack of motivation, using mother tongue and material related factors. Based on the results and discussions, some recommendations were given for both teachers and students in order to develop students speaking skill in English language, like: teachers should understand participatory ways of teaching, there should be 25 students in one class, students should be motivated to participate in speaking activity, teachers and students should minimize over use of mother tongue in English speaking classrooms were major recommendations.

Keywords: *Speaking skill; Participation; English language classrooms.*

1. Introduction

Language is a formal system of signs governed by grammatical rules of combinations to communicate meaning. This definition stresses the fact that human languages can be described as closed structural systems consisting of rules that relate particular signs to particular meanings (Bloomfield, 1914). English language serves as the language of instruction in secondary and higher education and as a necessary link with resource beyond the countries boundary such as diplomacy and of all international communications and generally it is the language through which modern style of life, science and technology are introduced. It has an important potential in education, commerce, government, international communication; and from this point of view it can be regarded as English is widely used in Ethiopia.

Over the last three decades, English has become the most important foreign language in the world. At present, English is the language for international communication; science; commerce; advertising; diplomacy and transmitting advanced technology (Willis, 1996). English language is the language of air and maritime navigation, of the worldwide web and of diplomacy, as well as the vehicle for international scientific exchange, and its pervasive presence can be felt in pop culture and the worldwide media (Judith, 2005).

The major goal of English language teaching should be to give learners the ability to use English effectively and accurately in communication (Davis and Pears, 1998). However, not all language learners after many years studying English can communicate fluently and accurately. Therefore, to overcome the problems that affect students' speaking skill, it is better to

participating students' on speaking skill of English language to make them effective speaker of the language.

The linkage between students' classroom participation and their academic achievement is undeniable (Lim, 1998). Studies have shown that when students participate actively in class, their academic achievement seems to be higher than those who are passive in classes. Students' participation includes many forms of students' actions such as speaking, listening, reading and writing and body language or physical movement (Lim, 1998). Littlewood (1996) stated that, the increasing in students' oral classroom participation should contribute to their improvement in English speaking proficiency.

Mohan (2003) states that, speech is similar to candle that gives light to darkroom as such like speech lightens the life of human beings because we express our opinions, wishes, feelings thoughts through speech. Speaking has many purposeful usages, although there are many factors that affect students' speaking skill participation in English.

2. Statement of the Problems

Luoma (1997) states that, speaking skill is one of the cornerstone in the issue of second or foreign language teaching and learning process. Our personality, our self-image, our knowledge of the world and our ability to reason out and express our thoughts are all related to in our spoken performance in a foreign language. Therefore, speaking skill needs to be effective by the English learners. However, many researchers express their compassion for the difficulties that the majority of students have faced in spoken English. Based on this, the following researchers conduct their study on the following titles and area:

Although a lot of research has been done on the factors affecting speaking skill internationally, very little has been conducted in Ethiopia. For instance: Tsegaye (1995) has conducted the research on speaking strategies employed by college students. Jenenew (2006) studied on how oral skills are taught in EFL speaking classrooms. Taye (2008) conducted the study on the comparative study on televised and non-televised speaking skill teaching techniques.

However, non-of these studies has covered an investigation on the factors affecting EFL learners' participation in speaking lesson in English classrooms. Therefore, the researcher believes that this area needs an attention to be researched. The current study will hope to fill the existing gap in this particular area in the country. Consequently, this heavily initiates the researcher to investigate the factors affecting EFL learners' participation in speaking lesson in English classrooms.

3. Basic Research Questions

This study was addressed the following basic research questions: Are there any material related factors that affect students' participation in speaking lesson?; What does the students' participation look like in English speaking lesson? and What do teachers do to let students to participate in English speaking lesson.

4. General Objective of the Study

The general objective of this study was to investigate the factors affecting EFL learners' participation in speaking lesson in English classrooms.

5. Specific Objectives of the Study

This study covered three specific objectives. These are: To identify material related factors that affect students' participation in speaking lesson; To find out what does the students' participation look like in English speaking lesson; and To assess how do teachers do to let students to participate in English speaking lesson.

6. Significance of the Study

The result of the current study regarding the factors affecting EFL learners' participation in speaking lesson in English will basically have the following key significances:

It may initiate or encourage students to overcome the speaking skill problems and to develop their speaking skill participation, because the current study tries to identify the problems that hinder their speaking ability in English so that the result of identification of the problems helps to enhance students in speaking skill of English language.

It can contribute for teachers to understand the ways of encouraging students' to develop their speaking ability and to know the mechanism of motivation that helps students' to accelerate their confidence in speaking skill of English. It can also help for English teachers to reconsider their attitude toward the factors that affect students' participation in speaking lesson in English classrooms and to understand the ways of helping students to participate actively in the area.

Hopefully, the study can contribute to the improvement of students' participation in speaking lesson in English language classroom and might show better teaching-learning for English learning at Shinshicho, Doyogena and Hedero Preparatory Schools and beyond.

7. Scope of the Study

The scope of this study was Southern Nation, Nationalities and People's Region of Ethiopia, particularly in Kembata Tembaro Zone because no research on this title is conducted in that area or location.

8. Research Design and Methodology

Both qualitative and quantitative methods were used for greater understanding of the problem under investigation. Qualitative and quantitative methods can be used to crosscheck the validity of the data and the derived conclusions. Therefore, the current study employed both qualitative and quantitative research methods to investigate the problem.

Research Design

The design of this study was descriptive research design. As to Kothari (2004), the focus of descriptive research design is concerned with describing the characteristics of a particular individual or of a group, or it concerned with specific predictions, with narration of facts and characteristics concerning individual, group or situations.

Research Setting

The current study was conducted in Southern, Nation, Nationalities and Peoples Regional State, particularly in Kembata Tembaro Zone on some selected preparatory schools (Shinshicho, Doyogena and Hedero Preparatory Schools). Kembata Tembaro zone comprises three nations from fifty-six Nations in Southern Regional State. The zone is 280 km away from Addis Ababa.

Population of the Study

Population of the current study were the students' of Shinshicho, Doyogena and Hedero Preparatory students who were enrolled in 2009 E.C. and the teachers who taught them English in the academic year in the selected preparatory schools were the population of the current study. Therefore, from 300 students, 147=males and 153=females were taken as sample representatives of participants of the study.

Sampling Techniques

For the this study, the researcher was used multi-stage sampling techniques. Kothari (2004) stated that, multi-stage sampling is used for big inquiries expanding to a considerably large geographical area, or under multi-stage sampling the first stage may be to select large primary sample units such as states, then district, then town and finally certain families within town. To select preparatory schools in the zone, then to select students and teachers in the selected schools, the researcher employed multi-stage sampling techniques.

Selection of Schools

To give equal quota for some selected preparatory schools, the researcher was applied quota sampling techniques. As indicated by Kothari and Garg (2014), quota sampling is generally that used when we have decided the specific characteristics (education, nationalities, geographical location, etc.) which we will base the quota. In the selected preparatory schools, a number of students vary from one

preparatory school to another preparatory school; however, they should have get equal quota to participate in the study rather than taking only one preparatory school to represent the rest selected preparatory schools in the zone. So that, the researcher has given 100 students quota for each preparatory schools in the zone which were selected for this study.

Selection of Students

To select students as respondent for the study, the researcher preferred the simple random sampling techniques. Therefore, the researcher chose units from the sampling frame randomly, for example, through a lottery. As stated by Walliman (2011) and Kothari and Garg (2014), the simple random selection procedure should aim to guarantee that each element (person, group, class, type etc.) has an equal chance of being selected. From the total number of students in each preparatory school, the researcher took 100 students by using simple random sampling techniques, so that the total sample size were 300 students from the selected preparatory schools (Shinshicho, Doyogena and Hedero) secondary and preparatory schools of the zone.

Selection of Teachers

To select the English teachers as information providers for the study, the researcher was applied non-probability sampling techniques. As stated by Belay and Abdinasir (2005), non-probability sampling techniques are convenient in situations when the number of sample to be selected is very small and the researcher wants to get some idea of the population characteristics in a short period of time. Therefore, all the teachers who taught grade 11 and 12 were taken as a respondents for the study. The size of the teacher respondents were twelve in number, to select them as a respondents, the researcher used availability or comprehensive sampling techniques.

Data Collection Instruments

The tools that the researcher used for this study were questionnaire, interviews and interview.

Questionnaire

The researcher used the questionnaire as the main data gathering tool for the current study. Both open-ended and close-ended questionnaire were designed for teachers and students to get necessary data from respondents for the current study. Five-point Likert-Scale type and Rating- Scale questions were developed for students and teachers. The questionnaire that designed for students and teachers were contained thirty (30) statements. There were 27 close-ended questions and 3 open-ended questions. The close-ended questions had (2-5) options which varied according to the question type.

Interview

In this study as a supplementary tool, the researcher used interview for students and teachers. That means, six selected teachers from Shishicho, Doyogena and Hedero Preparatory Schools and eight students who fill the questionnaire were selected by using purposive sampling techniques and they have been interviewed because it is difficult to interview all students and teachers who filled the questionnaire. Therefore, the researcher used maximum variation sampling to select students and teachers interviewee. Based on this sampling technique, the researcher selected top and low level achiever students for interview with help of English teacher to select them. To select teachers for interview, the researcher depended on their experience and educational status. Maximum variation sampling involves purposefully picking a wide range of variation on dimensions of interest. The type of interview that was used for this study was unstructured interview, to collect information in-depth from the interviewee. As Walliman (2011: 99), unstructured interview has a flexible format that is usually based on the questions guide. Accordingly, an interview guide, which has five (5) open-ended but unstructured items, was designed for students' and teachers' interviewees.

Classroom Observation

The researcher used classroom observation to see how the teachers carried out speaking lessons, how the students performed and what problems the students really encountered in speaking lessons in English classrooms. As to Guthrie (2014), observation allows the opportunity for validity check about whether people do what they say. The researcher observed eight classes from February 20-March 20/2009 E.C. To select the classes, researcher has discussed with English teacher at what days he/she teaches speaking lesson. After asking for permission from the teachers who were in charge of these two classes, the researcher observed each class in two periods (90 minutes). Each some selected preparatory schools were observed in different weeks, so two observations were made in a week. Therefore, totally eight classes were observed in one month interval. During observation, the researcher used classroom observation checklist. As stated in Calton and Covert (2007: 9), observation checklists were used to determine the presence or absence of an attribute and to count the prevalence of an item or event. Therefore, type of observation that the researcher used was non-participatory observation. Guthrie (2014) stated that, non-participatory observation is a type of observation that requires the researcher to be present in the situation, but not to participate in group action. Checklists were used to be completed by the researcher.

Data Gathering Procedures

The questionnaires were developed by the researcher and then the students' and teachers' questionnaire were piloted at Haile Mariam Mammo Preparatory School before taken it to main study area. Three hundred questionnaires were delivered to grade 11 and 12 students of Shishicho, Hedero and Doyogena Preparatory Schools 40 minutes before the classes began on different days. Before distributing the questionnaire the researcher introduced himself and the purpose of the data to the students. The researcher have given necessary information for the respondents on how to fill the questionnaire properly to get data. Then, the researcher encouraged all the respondents to fill out the questionnaire properly. On the same day, teachers' questionnaires were distributed to English teachers in their twenty five-minute break at the staff room. Twelve sheets of questionnaire were distributed for twelve English teachers in those some selected schools.

To gather data through interview, researcher confidently administered the students' and teachers' interview. With a friendly introducing himself and the purpose of interview, the researcher tried to clearly point out the objective and purpose of the study. The researcher precisely described and made clear the ideas to make it understandable for the interviewee.

To gather data through classroom observation, the researcher observed the needed classes without commenting on the teaching-learning process. During the classroom observation, the researcher watched the actual teaching-learning to fill the observation checklist in order to get the necessary data for the current study.

Data Analysis

Data were organized according to the objectives. Relevant themes were selected and coded. Item analysis were used for qualitative data. In quantitative data, tallies were converted into frequencies and percentages. The researcher classified the raw data into some purposeful and coding operation was usually done at this stage and the researcher edited the data that enables the researcher to improve the quality of data. And finally, the data were recorded accordingly by using quantitative and qualitative methods or by using numbers and words to interpret data. In order to answer the three research questions, the descriptive statistics of frequencies and percentages were used. The statistical analysis was conducted utilizing the Statistical Package of Social Science (SPSS).

7. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the data gained from students' and teachers' through questionnaires, interview and classroom observation.

Discussion of Students' and Teachers' Questionnaire

Table.1: Students' response on the techniques and strategies used by the teachers

s/n	Items	Responses					Total	
		Always	Usually	Sometimes	Rarely	Never		
1	My English teacher asks by using as a	Freq	160	90	40	10	-	300
		%	53.3%	30%	13.3%	3.33%	-	100%
2	My English teacher answer by using	Freq	165	89	44	2	-	300
		%	55	29.7%	14.6%	0.6%	-	100%
3	My English teacher encourage group	Freq	-	-	10	200	90	300
		%	-	-	3.3%	66.7%	30%	100%
4	My English teacher allow me to make	Freq	-	-	-	40	260	300
		%	-	-	-	13.3%	86.7%	100%
5	My teacher allow me to make	Freq	-	-	-	20	280	300
		%	-	-	-	6.67%	93.3%	100%
6	My English teacher gives instruction on	Freq	278	12	10	-	-	300
		%	92.6%	4%	3.33%	-	-	100%
7	My English teacher allows me to correct	Freq	155	100	-	45	-	300
		%	51.6%	33.4%	-	15%	-	100%
8	My English teacher presets pronunciation	Freq	-	-	-	30	270	300
		%	-	-	-	10%	90%	100%
9	My English teacher designs good speaking	Freq	-	-	-	110	190	300
		%	-	-	-	36.6%	63.4%	100%
10	My English teacher uses learner-centered	Freq	-	-	-	20	280	300
		%	-	-	-	6.66%	93.3%	100%
11	My English teacher gives enough time to	Freq	5	16	-	80	189	300
		%	1.66%	5.33%	-	26.6%	63%	100%
12	My English teacher does not allow	Freq	180	97	-	13	10	300
		%	60%	32%	-	4.33%	3.33%	100%

Table.2: Students response on the strategies and role that they used.

13	I speak English only inside the classroom	Freq.	145	126	20	9	-	300
		%	48%	42%	6.66%	3%	-	100%
14	I can make a phone conversation in	Freq.	-	-	7	23	270	300
		%	-	-	2.33%	7.6%	270%	100%
15	I actively participate in the classroom	Freq.	-	4	7	110	179	300
		%	-	1.33%	2.33%	36.7%	59.7%	100%
16	I like to present my group's idea to the	Freq.	14	35	77	120	94	300
		%	4.66%	11.67%	25.7%	40%	31.3%	
17	I watch and listen to English TV& radio	Freq.	7	8	55	118	112	300

		%	2.33%	2.67%	18.33%	39.3%	37.3%	
18	I watch & listen TV & radio programs to	Freq.	2	4	24	130	140	300
		%	0.66%	1.33%	8%	43.3%	46.7%	100%
19	I have confidence in English speaking	Freq.	20	27	-	155	98	300
		%	6.66%	9%	-	51.7%	32.6%	100%
20	I am motivated in participating in English	Freq.	5	9	-	126	160	300
		%	1.66%	3%	-	42%	53.4%	100%
22	I always prefer to speak in mother	Freq.	107	131	-	30	22	300
		%	35.6%	43.7%	-	10%	7.33%	100%

Table.3: Students' response that related to their grammar and vocabulary knowledge.

s/n	Items		Responses		Total
			Yes	No	
22	Do you have a good knowledge of English grammar that led you to	Freq.	75	225	300
		%	25%	75%	100%
23	Do you have a knowledge of English vocabulary that can let you to	Freq.	67	233	300
		%	22.33%	77.66%	100%

Table.4: Students' response that related to their learning-environment and learning-materials.

No.	Items		Responses		Total
			Yes	No	
24	In my class there are more than fifty students	Freq.	300	-	300
		%	100%	-	100%

25	Is your class arranged in the ways that facilitate you to participate in speaking lesson?	Freq.	10	290	300
		%	3.3%	96.7%	100%
26	Do you have a spoken laboratories in the school that facilitates your participation in speaking lesson of English?	Freq.	-	300	300
		%	-	100%	100%
27	Are there varieties of audio and video materials in your school that you use as a model for practice speaking?	Freq.	-	300	300
		%	-	100%	100%

Freq=frequency

To assure you on the discussion of data, students' and teachers were asked the same questions. As stated in the above tables 1-4 the following discussions were made. Based on the results, the following were teachers, students, and learning environment and material related factors that were likely affect students' participation in speaking lesson in English Language classrooms.

Teachers related factors:

Teachers were not playing vital roles in developing students' English speaking skills. It was found that current Preparatory School English teaching ran contrary to the students' expectation and preferences. As indicated on discussion part, teachers do not used group discussion in speaking lesson in English classrooms, to encourage students' participation in

speaking lesson. With its distinctive features, the English classroom was teacher-dominated one and students only played passive roles. That means, teachers most of the time controlled the class by doing most of the speaking activities and directing all the language production.

Most of the time, the teachers were obsessed with correcting their students' errors. This might have made the students passive recipients waiting for direction and afraid of making mistakes. As indicated on discussion part most of the time teacher correct students mistakes during speaking lesson. They did not used the techniques, strategies, and activities that could be employed in speaking class in order to enhance students to speak in English. The following points are the techniques and strategies those were not employed by the teachers: pairs or group discussion in

the speaking classroom, letting students' to make dialogue and conversation in speaking classroom, they did not let students to listen to the records on the radio or video and present an idea back to the class, they did not let students to practice and participate speaking through individual or group presentation, they were not presenting some pronunciation points to help students' develop their English fluency.

Teachers had designed poor speaking activities, gave less time to various speaking activities, and they did not allow students to speak with poor pronunciation. Teachers did not also use learners- centered approach in speaking classes.

Students related factors:

The results of the study indicated that the students faced many problems. They spoke very little or not at all in English during speaking lesson in English language classrooms; they could not think of anything to say in English during speaking lesson in English language. They used mother tongue instead of English when they discussed in groups or in pairs. Their participation was low in speaking lesson in English language classrooms. Students lacked motivation to speak. The results of study also showed that there were another factors affecting students' participation in speaking lesson in English language classrooms were: lack of enough grammar knowledge or topical knowledge, lack of enough English vocabulary knowledge, lack of confidence to speak in English language or unwillingness to speak target language, pressure to perform well or worrying not to make mistakes during speaking English in the classroom.

Most students have little encouragement to use English outside the classroom, students speak little English only inside the classroom. As a result, the use of English only inside the classroom was another factor that hinders the successful of the students' participation in speaking lesson in English classrooms.

The study findings revealed that students were not actively participating in the classroom discussion; they did not encourage themselves to perform speaking activities in the classroom, they did not watch and listen to the foreign English mass media programs (BBC, CNN), in order to develop their speaking skill and listening comprehension. These were also founded as the factors which impede students' English speaking performances.

Learning-environment and material related factors:

There were also learning-environmental and material related factors as well. Classes were large in size, there were large number of students or more than sixty students in one class at Shinshicho, Doyogena and Hederro Preparatory School that was challenging for teachers to expose students in

practice speaking activities, the classroom were not arranged in the way that could develop students speaking skills. In the schools, there was no language laboratory and there were no various audio and video materials in the Shinshicho, Doyogena and Hederro Preparatory Schools in the Zone in order to enhance students' speaking skill.

8. Conclusion

Based on the results, the following were teacher related factors that were likely affect students'

participation in speaking lesson in English Language classrooms:

Teachers were not playing vital roles in developing students' English speaking skills. Teachers do not used group discussion in speaking lesson in English classrooms, to encourage students' participation in speaking lesson. With its distinctive features, the English classroom was teacher- dominated one and students only played passive roles. Most of the time, the teachers were obsessed with correcting their students' errors. This might have made the students passive recipients waiting for direction and afraid of making mistakes.

They did not used the techniques, strategies, and activities that could be employed in speaking class in order to enhance students to speak in English: pairs or group discussion in the speaking classroom, letting students' to make dialogue and conversation in speaking classroom, they did not let students to listen to the records on the radio or video and present an idea back to the class, they did not let students to practice and participate speaking through individual or group presentation, they were not presenting some pronunciation points to help students' develop their English fluency.

Teachers had designed poor speaking activities, gave less time to various speaking activities, and they did not allow students to speak with poor pronunciation. Teachers did not also use learners- centered approach in speaking classes. Therefore, these were among the factors affecting students' learning English speaking skills related to the teachers' use of the techniques and strategies.

There were also many students' related factors. These were: They spoke very little or not at all in English during speaking lesson in English language classrooms; they could not think of anything to say in English during speaking lesson in English language. They used mother tongue instead of English when they discussed in groups or in pairs. Their participation was low in speaking lesson in English language classrooms. Students lacked motivation to speak. Another factors were affecting students': lack of enough grammar knowledge

or topical knowledge, lack of enough English vocabulary knowledge, lack of confidence to speak in English language or unwillingness to speak target language, pressure to perform well or worrying not to make mistakes during speaking English in the classroom. Most students have little encouragement to use English outside the classroom, students speak little English only inside the classroom.

The study findings revealed that students were not actively participating in the classroom discussion; they did not encourage themselves to perform speaking activities in the classroom, they did not watch and listen to the foreign English mass media programs (BBC, CNN), in order to develop their speaking skill and listening comprehension.

Also there were learning-environmental and material related factors as well. These were: classes were large in size, there were large number of students or more than sixty students in one class at Shinshicho, Doyogena and Hedero Preparatory School that was challenging for teachers to expose students in practice speaking activities, the classroom were not arranged in the way that could develop students speaking skills. In the schools, there was no language laboratory. The results of the findings also revealed that there were no various audio and video materials in the Shinshicho, Doyogena and Hedero Preparatory Schools in the Zone in order to enhance students' speaking skill.

9. Recommendations

Based on the results of the study, some recommendations were made for both teachers and students at Shinshicho, Doyogena and Hedero Preparatory Schools.

As for the teachers, they should help their students to overcome inhibition and shyness by having friendly, helpful and cooperative behaviors to make students feel comfortable when speaking in the class, reminding students not to worry about making mistakes and giving them a clear instructions and sufficient guidance. Teachers should simplify the topics in the textbook to make them easier, more interesting and relevant to their lives to let students in practice and participation.

Teachers should provide maximum opportunity to students to speak the target language by providing a rich environment that contains collaborative work, authentic materials and tasks, and shared knowledge. Teachers should provide the vocabulary in the given topic beforehand that students need in speaking activities. They should let students to practice English speaking through dialogues, conversation, picture description, debating, storytelling, and listening to the records on the radio or video and present the idea back to the whole class.

Teachers should play their role in facilitating, guiding, motivating, and supervising the students' in participating in speaking activities in English. Teachers should also use learners-centered approach in order to let students' into practice. They should provide some pronunciation points in the lesson to develop students' English fluency. Teachers should give students more opportunities to speak English in class by using some speaking activities that require students to speak. Teachers should decide carefully when and how to correct the students' mistakes so that the students are not fearful of making mistakes and the flow of the students' conversation is should not be destroyed.

They should reduce teacher speaking time in class while increasing student speaking time. Step back and observe students. They should encourage students to participate in speaking activities. Teachers should try to involve each student in every speaking activity. To finalize, teachers should have to choose and use appropriate teaching materials or aids that promote students' participation in speaking lesson in English language classrooms; that means, they should use audio and video materials (radio, records and Television or disc visual drives record. They should create an English speaking environment by letting them for watching films or videos in English. Teachers should also use English in the classroom frequently so that the students have more exposure to the language.

Some of the recommendations drawn from findings for students were: Students should play their role by participating in speaking lesson in English language classrooms. In a class, more discussion and communication should be in English, the more the students should be familiar with the practice. So, pair work, group work and discussion should be in class in English. Students should have to participate actively in speaking activities in English classrooms such as asking and answering questions on speaking activities, asking for clarity during speaking, group and pair discussions, presenting what they discussed or listened, asking for information, giving information and advice, giving opinion, telling stories, playing language games and solving problems. They should not worry about making mistakes during speaking. Students should communicate with their classmate in English not only inside the classroom but outside their classrooms in English. Students should be autonomous learners.

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